

TABLE 2. SIMULTANEOUS MICRODETERMINATION OF LEAD AND MERCURY(II)

Pb (No ₃) ₂ (ml)	Hippuric acid (ml) taken	Lead (mg) found	Mercuric chloride	Hippuric acid (ml) taken	Mercury (mg) found
0.01M	0.0249M		0.01M	0.249M	
0.2	0.16	0.4144	0.5	0.40	0.3996
0.3	0.24	0.6230	0.4	0.32	0.5990
0.4	0.32	0.8288	0.3	0.24	0.7990
0.5	0.40	1.0360	0.2	0.16	0.9990

In Table 2, lead and mercury (II) have been titrated together in the ascending order from the top; while making calculations for lead and mercury (II), the observed values have been divided by 2, since the complex between lead and hippuric acid or mercury (II) and hippuric acid takes place in the ratio 1:2.

It has been observed that the complexes between lead or mercury and hippuric acid are formed at p^H 6.1 and 5.2 respectively.

The present method is direct, simple and very much less time consuming than other methods, already described.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R. for providing financial assistance. One of the authors (J.V.G.K.) is grateful to the management of P. S. G. College of Technology for the encouragement in this work.

References

1. E. HOFFMANN and A. SARACZ., *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **199**, 6.
2. D. NEGGIN and A. KRIZ., *Anolele Univ. "C. I. PARHON" Bucuresh. Ser. Stiint. Naf. Chem.* 1962, **1135**, 117.
3. A. I. IVANKOVA., D. N. PRINOVA and D. P. SHCHERBOV., *Prom. Khis. Reaktivov osobo chist. Veshchestre.* 1967, **8**, 174.
4. H. KHALIFA., *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **203**, 151.
5. A. MURATA, H. TAKUSHI, K. FUJIYASU and T. SUZUKI., *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1966, **13**, 143.
6. G. G. BOMBI and M. FIORAM., *Talanta*, 1965, **12**, 1053.
7. G. K. SINGHAL and K. N. TANDON., *Talanta*, 1967, **14**, 1351.
8. J. CHWASTOWSKA., *Proc. Conf. Appl. Phys. Chem. methods. Chem. Anal. Budapest*, 1966, **1**, 45.
9. L. M. ANDREASOV, E. I. VAIL, V. A. KREMER, Z. N. CHERNYAeva and S. A. REZNICHENKE., *IZU. Vysh. Vchev. Zaved. Khim Khim Tekhnol.*, 1967, **10**, 743.
10. O. C. SAXENA., *Mikrochim. Acta.* 1967, **1123**.
11. J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY., and O. C. SAXENA., *U.A.R.J. chem.* 1970, **13**, 375.

Some Aspects on the Isolation of UCl₄·2Ph₂SO·2H₂O and a Study of its Electronic Spectra and Magnetic Susceptibility

A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700032

Manuscript received 19 September 1973; revised 17 May 1974; accepted 23 May 1974

IN a previous communication¹ it was pointed out that the title compound could only be isolated provided the reactants, UCl₄ and Ph₂SO are mixed in a mole proportion less than 1 : 2. Some further precautionary measures, which are essential for the isolation of the above compound are being outlined here.

1. The hydrochloric acid solution of UO₂Cl₂ prepared from U₃O₈ should not be evaporated upto extremely dry condition; this slightly moist residue should be taken up with ether for reduction with zinc and hydrogen chloride.

2. It was found preferable to use small amount of zinc granules and to allow more time for the completion of the reduction process than to use excess zinc dust to accelerate the rate of reduction. Use of excess zinc dust leads to deposition of UCl₄ on it, thereby modifying the UCl₄ : Ph₂SO ratio, resulting in the deposition of UCl₄ · 2Ph₂SO.

The compound shows 2: 1 electrolytic behaviour in methanol² and so it is presumed that the complex species undergoes solvolytic reactions³⁻⁵ in the above solvent. The substance behaves as a weak electrolyte in acetonitrile and the ionisation is far less evidenced from the very low conductance value (Ca 20 Ohm⁻¹ Cm²) at Ca 10⁻²M solution; and so a 2.20 x 10⁻² molar solution (nearly a saturated solution) of the substance in acetonitrile has been considered suitable for the measurement of the electronic spectra (in the visible region) as no other non-interacting solvent is capable of keeping the compound in solution. The visible band (25-10k) with their likely origins are given in the table. It was not possible to record the f transitions in the spectra of this substance in the long wavelength range for want of a suitable instrument.

TABLE—THE OPTICAL SPECTRAL BANDS OF UCl₄·2Ph₂SO·2H₂O IN ACETONITRILE AND THEIR LIKELY ORIGINS.

Terminal level	Band positions (Cm ⁻¹)	ε _{max}
3F ₃ , 3F ₄	10,870 - 12,200	4.10 for 10870 Cm ⁻¹ band (others are broad shoulders)
3H ₆	14,710; 15,270	25.2; 19.5
1D ₂	16,670 (Sh)	—
3P ₁	17,860	7.7
1I ₆	20,240; 21,550	10.9; 8.9; 13.4
	22,470	
3P ₂	23,040	11.8

Assuming the 5f² configuration for U(IV) ion, the bands in the spectra are assigned⁶ to transitions from the ground state ³H₄ to other levels within the configuration 5f² (the table). The overall energy span of the levels within the configuration depends on: (1) ligand field, (2) extent of inter electronic repulsion and (3) spin orbit coupling interactions⁷. So, the additional splitting of the bands observed is due to the elimination of (2J+1) fold degeneracy of the individual levels. This may be due to significant interaction with the ligand field.

From the spectral data, Lande splitting parameter, ϵ_{3p} , $[= \Delta\nu_i/(J+1)]$, where $\Delta\nu = ({}^3P_2) - ({}^3P_1)$ and $J+1=2$ for $U(IV)^8$ is calculated and shown below. Here the energy difference between the two 3p levels is taken as a measure of the effect of the ligand field or of the covalency effect. So, the position of

$UCl_4 \cdot 2Ph_2SO \cdot 2H_2O$ is in between $UCl_4 \cdot 4 Me_2SO$ and $UCl_4 \cdot 3Ph_2SO$ with respect to the ligand field or covalency effect.

As already reported¹, the μ_{eff} of the complex is 2.05 B.M. which is quite low for the spin only value of the two unpaired electrons. Assuming no thermal population of excited states, like the octahedral complexes, the susceptibility appears to be due to an unusually large 'high frequency term'¹⁰ which may arise primarily from interaction between ground state and the excited state. Slightly lower value found here than the value observed for UCl_6^{2-} by Day and Venanzi¹¹ is due to the higher field created in the compound $UCl_4 \cdot 2Ph_2SO \cdot 2H_2O$ than in the UCl_6^{2-} complex.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1970, 95.
2. R. G. HAYTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 3046.
3. A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 4296.
4. R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and D. C. BERA, *Indian J. Chem. (In Press)*.
5. R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and D. C. BERA, (Communicated).
6. C. A. HUTCHISON and G. A. CANDELA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 707.
7. R. PAPPALARADO and C. K. JORGENSEN, *Helv. Phys. Acta*, 1964, **37**, 79.
8. J. TRZEBIOTOWSKA and K. BUKIETYUSKA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **19**, 38.
9. J. SELBIN, N. SCHÖBER and J. P. ORTEGO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1385.
10. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, N. Y. 1962.
11. J. P. DAY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, A, 197.

Polarographic Studies of Tl(I)-Ethanolamine Systems

J. K. BHADRA, P. BANDYOPADHYAY & B. K. SEN

Inorganic Chemical Laboratories, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

Manuscript received 8 November 1973; revised 1 April 1974; accepted 23 May 1974

THALLIUM (I) ion has little tendency towards complex formation and this is reflected in the fact that the half-wave potential of thallium(I) ion is independent of most of the supporting electrolytes¹. Of the few complexes formed by this element, oxygen donor ligands are prominent in contrast to nitrogen

donor functions. The present communication reports the polarographic investigation of thallos ion in presence of monoethanolamine (MEA), diethanolamine (DEA), N-methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) and triethanolamine (TEA) at low sodium hydroxide concentration with a view to study the relative ability of these ligands towards complexation with Tl (I). It has been found that the complexing ability follows the order,

The electrode process in each case was found to be slightly irreversible.

Experimental

Thallium (I) perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving thallium (I) carbonate (A. R.) in perchloric acid (A. R.) and standardised as thallium (I) chromate. The ethanolamines were of reagent quality. Other chemicals were of appropriate purity. The test solution was prepared by mixing solutions of thallium (I) perchlorate, sodium hydroxide, ethanolamine and sodium perchlorate in sufficient quantity to make the final solutions of unit ionic strength. No maximum suppressor was found necessary.

Polarograms were recorded with a Cambridge pen-recording polarograph with a D.M.E. having a capillary characteristics of $m = 1.624$ mg/sec and $t = 3.797$ sec at 0.5vvs S.C.E. To avoid contamination of chloride ions, a double bridge of agar-sodium perchlorate (2M), sodium perchlorate solution (2M) and agar-sodium perchlorate (2M) was used to connect the test solution with the calomel electrode in saturated sodium chloride. Total resistance of the cell was negligible. The test solutions were deaerated by passing electrolytic hydrogen gas. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$ unless otherwise stated.

Results and Discussion

The α_n values for each of the systems were calculated from the plots of $\log i'(i_i)$ against E. The values were slightly less than unity (Table 1). The limiting current for each of the systems was found to be diffusion controlled as indicated by the constant value of $i_d/h^{1/2}$ (h = effective height of mercury column).

Polarograms recorded in solutions of $10^{-3}M$ Tl(I) containing 0.1M sodium hydroxide and 1.0M ethanolamines (and also in absence of any ligand) in a temperature range of 5° to 30° showed that the half-wave potentials were constant within $\pm 0.01V$ but the diffusion current increased with the increase in temperature. Plot of $\ln i_d$ vs $1/T$ gave straight lines from the slopes of which the activation energies of diffusion² were calculated (Table 1).

The diffusion currents (i_d) increased linearly with the Tl (I) concentration within $0.2 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ in 1.0M ethanolamines and 0.1M sodium hydroxide. The values of the diffusion current constants are given in Table 1.